

DIVERSiplotter – A tool for field data visualisation based on the DIVERSify intercropping trials

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Summary

The generation of multiple complex field trial datasets presents challenges on how information is efficiently stored, visualized and queried to ease downstream analysis. Ensuring that data is held both in ways appropriate for these data types and to aid the efficient querying will help scientists to gain as much insight as possible from patterns in the data and the underlying causes. We have developed a prototype web-based platform called DIVERSiplotter which we have initially made publicly available to project partners within the EU-funded project DIVERSify (Horizon2020, grant no. 727284. www.plant-teams.eu) for feedback but hope to make it more generally available to the community. DIVERSiplotter presents an interactive and engaging expandable platform to allow users to explore and interact with intercropping field trial data collected as part of the DIVERSify project. We have integrated data for 94 traits, 11 species, 48 varieties across three plant partners and seven trial sites across Europe.

Key words: Intercropping, DIVERSify, DIVERSiplotter, Horizon2020

Introduction

Intercropping addresses issues linked to modern farming, such as high levels of pests and pathogens, moderate yield, soil degradation and high input requirements such as labour and additional nutrients (Brooker *et al.*, 2014). It achieves this by growing two or more crops together to their mutual benefit. This relationship and the benefit are expressed and quantifiable in trait data measurements taken over multiple years and trial sites across project partner locations. Careful preparation and execution of the data collection, processing, management, visualisation and analysis steps are essential in extracting the most valuable information from the data. It is crucial to make this data available under the FAIR principles to ensure it is findable, accessible, interoperable and reproducible (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016) with the goal of maximum exploitation.

Visualisations are a powerful tool in the discovery of hidden knowledge in data. The human brain has an incredibly high capacity for pattern recognition (Mattson, 2014). Interactive visualizations and query interfaces allow for the visual exploration of data and facilitate the discovery of information such as patterns which are difficult to see in raw data. Effective visualisations can help uncover correlations between traits, clusters of plant individuals expressing a certain characteristic or data outliers, all of which are valuable information.

Fig. 1. Database schema: The data is broken down into its basic entities and their relationships which are manifested in the database tables and foreign key restraints.

Materials and Methods

All DIVERSify project data has been collected and collated in a synchronized way using standard Microsoft Excel spreadsheet templates specifically designed to hold intercropping data across different years and locations. Subsequently, these files were pre-processed using R (<https://www.r-project.org>) where they were checked for errors, cleaned and merged (Pappagallo *et al.*, n.d.). A custom MySQL (<https://www.mysql.com>) database was developed to not only facilitate and ensure the long-term storage of the project data, but also to act as the backbone of the web-facing visualization and query interface (Fig. 1). The database comprises 11 tables, seven views and two stored procedures enabling the storage of the intercropping data at three levels: plot, species and individual plant. Outputs from the R data cleansing script were imported into the database using custom data upload code written in Java.

Access to the data within the DIVERSify database is enabled via a representational state transfer (REST) application programming interface (API) written in Java. This has a number of advantages including allowing programmatic access to data to project partners through common standard interfaces and maintaining a programming language agnostic interface on which new tools can be developed.

The public-facing web interface was designed and developed using current web standards using the reactive web framework Vue.js (<https://vuejs.org>) which facilitates rapid prototyping, and a short development cycle permitting fast incorporation of feedback from researchers and users. This is important as we develop this tool using an iterative design pattern. The visualisations of DIVERSiplotter use the open source graphing library Plotly (<https://plotly.com/javascript/>). All visualisations throughout DIVERSiplotter use a colour-blind safe palette to ensure accessibility. We have developed the system to use open source tools to ensure it is freely, and openly available to interested groups and we encourage its download and contribution from the community through our GitHub page (<https://github.com/cropgeeks/>).

We have provided an initial version of DIVERSiplotter from <https://ics.hutton.ac.uk/diversify/> which is available to explore and will be updated when new versions are released.

Results

The web-based interface of DIVERSiplotter currently offers four types of visualisations: plot-level data looking at traits recorded across the whole plot, species-level data describing the performance of individual species within a plot, variety-focused visualisations looking at the differences between cultivars grown as monocultures and together with other varieties and finally trait-focused visualisations comparing data across recording levels from a trait point of view and highlighting patterns like correlations between traits.

Plot-level data

Plot-level data is broken down by location and year. A table shows statistical measurements like minimum, maximum, average and standard deviation for each trait. Boxplots for each selected trait, location and year combination visually show these statistical values for the crop combinations grown in the experiment. Fig. 2 shows an exemplar visualisation comparing weed biomass and vegetative yield for faba bean, faba bean together with wheat and wheat individually. Faba bean exhibits a high vegetative yield compared to wheat and their combination, not surprisingly, lies in-between. Weed biomass in the intercropping plots on the other hand is reduced compared to the monocultures.

Fig. 2. Monoculture vs intercropping: Weed biomass and vegetative yield plotted for faba bean and wheat monocultures compared to the intercropping result of growing both crops together. The combined plot shows a low weed biomass compared to the faba bean monoculture and exhibits a vegetative yield between that of faba bean and wheat monocultures.

Fig. 3. Plant cultivar grain yield across different locations: Grain yield of different species and crops is grouped by location and suggests an impact of climate or soil on plant performance. Hovering over a box plot reveals the quartile values of the respective cultivar and location.

Fig. 4. Variety monoculture versus intercropping: Average trait values are plotted per trait (y-axis grouping) where each individual bar represents either a monoculture or an intercropping plot with the monoculture always on top.

Fig. 5 Trait scatter matrix: Four traits plotted against one another to highlight correlations, clusters and outliers in the data. The colouring is based on the crop present in the plot and emphasises their individual characteristics. Hovering over data points reveals the trait values and the crop underlying the data point. Selections made using the rectangle or lasso mechanism highlight the selected data points in all other trait combinations for easier identification of the same groupings.

Species-level data

The second type of visualisation in DIVERSiplotter utilises the species-level data to generate charts highlighting the performance of individual species, both within and across crops and across trial locations. Fig. 3 shows an example of this type of visualisation. The x-axis is grouped by trial location and the y-axis shows grain yield. Species grown per location are represented by one box plot per location, assuming the species was grown at this trial site. This kind of chart supports different ways of investigating the presented data. The grouping by location allows comparisons of the same species across different climates and possibly soil properties, while the individual groups underline the different characteristics of species grown at the same location. Going forwards we will look into incorporating time as a third perspective onto the data facilitating comparisons between growing seasons.

Variety-focused visualisations

When dealing with intercropping trials, one question of key interest is how plant teams compare to monocultures. An intuitive visualisation technique for this scenario is to look at trait data averages for a variety monoculture and compare this to the average results for this variety in plant teams. Fig. 4 shows an exemplar plot of this type comparing the canopy height and cover percentage for the faba bean (*Vicia faba*) variety Julia. On its own Julia exhibits a canopy height of 84 cm, similar to the canopy height combined with Elison (*Avena sativa* variety) and SPL (*Lathyrus sativus* variety), whereas its combination with Cornetto and Tybalt (both *Triticum aestivum* varieties) reduces the average canopy height to around 60 cm. Comparing this result to the cover percentage, we see that this is also reduced for the combination with Tybalt; however, the combination with Cornetto shows an increased cover percentage.

Trait-focused visualisations

The final type of visualisation in DIVERSiplotter turns the approach on its head and looks at overall patterns in the data by plotting selected traits against each other in a scatter plot matrix (SPLOM). SPLOMs are an extremely useful tool for looking at data at a very high level by covering several trait combinations at once. Each individual chart shows the data plotted for two of the selected traits. By organising them in a matrix, patterns showing up in one subplot can easily be seen in the other trait combinations.

Looking at the example in Fig. 5, we see that the Styrian Scarlet runner bean (*Phaseolus coccineus*) forms a distinct cluster in the combination of grain yield and seed weight, because of its high seed weight. That same cluster is distinctly visible, albeit compressed, in the subplot to the left where seed weight is plotted against biomass. Looking down one sub-plot from the original sub-plot to grain yield and seed weight, however, we are no longer able to distinguish this cluster from the rest of the data.

Another interesting example is the combination of grain yield and biomass. Two separate correlations between these two traits are visible. The steep correlation includes crops like corn, sorghum and Styrian Scarlet runner bean, while all crops are correlated in a broader, less steep cluster.

Discussion

We have developed an open source, web-based platform for the storage, querying and visualisation of intercropping data over several years and across multiple locations. The intuitive visualisations allow, among many other examples, the interactive exploration of the underlying data, comparisons between different crop combinations and highlighting the effects of intercropping versus monocultures for key traits. Going forwards, new data will be added to the system as it becomes available from DIVERSify field trials. Additional visualisation types will be added as required to ensure the most valuable information can be extracted from raw data. We will gather additional feedback from other researchers and end-users to further improve the usability of the system. DIVERSiplotter will be beneficial to all partners during the project and will be a valuable data resource for the intercropping community after the project has ended. DIVERSiplotter was developed as an intercropping database and visualisation tool that is not closely tied to this project. It therefore has the potential to be of use to other intercropping projects as an already established platform.

References

Brooker R W, Bennett A E, Cong W F, Daniell T J, George T S, Hallett P D, Hawes C, Iannetta P P M, Jones H G, Karley A J, Li L, McKenzie B M, Pakeman R J, Paterson E, Schöb C, Shen J, Squire G, Watson C A, Zhang C, Zhang F, Zhang J, White P J. 2014. Improving intercropping: a synthesis of research in agronomy, plant physiology and ecology. *New Phytologist* **206(1):107–117. <http://doi:10.1111/nph.13132>.**

Mattson M P. 2014. Superior pattern processing is the essence of the evolved human brain. *Frontiers in Neuroscience* **8**:265. <http://doi:10.3389/fnins.2014.00265>.

Pappagallo S, Brandmeier J, Banfield-Zanin J A, Kiær L, P Shaw P, Raubach S, Karley A J, Scherber C. 2021. Coordinating data collection in intercropping: A feasible example. *Aspects of Applied Biology* **146**, *Intercropping for Sustainability 2021*, pp. xx–xx.

Wilkinson M, Dumontier M, Aalbersberg I, Appleton G, Axton M, Baak A, Blomberg N, da Silva Santos L O B, Bourne P, Bouwman J, Brookes A J, Clark T, Crosas M, Dillo I, Dumon O, Evelo C, Finkers R, González-Beltrán A, Gray A J G, Growth P, Grethe J, Heringa J, Hoen P A C T, Hooft R, Kuhn T, Kok R, Kok J, Lusher S J, Martone M, Mons A, Packer A L, Rocca-Serra B P P, Roos M, van Schaik R, Sansone S-A, Schultes E, Sengstag T, Mason Slater T, Strawn G O, Swertz M, Thompson M, van der Lei J, van Mulligen E M, Velterop J, Waagmeester A, Wittenburg P, Wolstencroft K, Zhao J, Mons B. 2016. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data* **3**:1–9. <http://doi:10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

